

First records of *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930, was described from the Democratic Republic of Congo based on a single female. Here we report on a female from South Africa for the first time. The general morphology and distribution of the species is discussed with notes on its lifestyle. The male is still unknown.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Aethriscus Pocock, 1902 is a rare African genus of orb-weaver spider family Araneidae known only from two African species (World Spider Catalog, 2026). It is listed in the subfamily Cyrtarachninae in the Cyrtarachnini. Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily that is notable for its highly specialized predatory strategies, especially moth specialization, unusual web architectures, such as spanning-thread webs, triangular webs, and bolas, while some are webless with effective using masquerade and chemical deception (Stowe, 1986; Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014). The group was first established by Simon (1892), originally as Cyrtarachneae, and has since been treated at different taxonomic ranks (Sharff & Coddington 2020; *et al.*, 2014).

Little is known about the behaviour of the *Aethriscus* species, only that they are known as bird-dropping spiders. They rely on extreme crypsis and immobility when resting, resembling bird droppings. This is supported by their shiny bodies and short legs that fold around the body (Figs 1 & 4). When a spider is seen but misidentified as uninteresting by predators, it is a form of defensive mimicry called masquerade. Masquerade is a special type of protective mimicry where an organism avoids being eaten by resembling an inanimate object that predators normally ignore, such as a twig, leaf, stone, or bird dropping. The key idea is misidentification: the predator sees the organism but mistakenly identifies it as something that is not food. This enables the spiders to rest unnoticed during the day in exposed places on the upper surface of leaves.

Although *Aethriscus* is recorded from two African countries, very few specimens have been collected, and few field observations have been made. *Aethriscus olivaceus* Pocock, 1902 and *A. pani* Lessert, 1930, are known only from females, and both were described from the Democratic Republic of Congo and recollected from South Africa. *Aethriscus olivaceus* was first reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), and in this paper, we provide the first records of *A. pani* from South Africa.

METHODS

A female *A. pani* was collected in 2026 in Gauteng and the specimen was kept alive in a large terrarium. She died and a voucher specimen is deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Institute in Pretoria. Data sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform, resulted in only one additional record (Fig. 4) from the Limpopo province.

TAXONOMY

Diagnostic characters: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 was described from Democratic Republic of Congo. Female total length 10 mm. Carapace is fawn, smooth and shiny with blackish hue; with small tubercles present at the cephalic region constriction; the carapace is wider than long with sides rounded, narrowed in eye region (Fig. 3). Eyes in two rows (Fig. 5) with the median and lateral eyes on tubercles (Figs 5 & 9) and the median eyes closely group, three times closer to each other than the laterals; anterior eyes slightly larger than posterior eyes.

Figure 1–3. *Aethriscus pani* female from Gauteng. 1. Anterior view. 2. Ventral view. 3. Dorsal view. Credit: John Leroy.

Figure 4–5. *Aethriscus pani*. 4. Female from Ohrigstad, dorsal view showing their resemblance to bird droppings. 5. Anterior view showing the eye pattern. Credits: 4. Sharpview. 5. John Leroy.

Figure 6–11. *Aethriscus pani* female. 6–7. Epigyne. 8. Habitus line drawing, dorsal view. 9. Anterior view. 10. Posterior view. 11. Ventral view. Credits: 9–11. John Leroy; 6 & 8. After Lessert (1930).

Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen smooth and shiny covering almost half of the cephalothorax; twice as wide (19 mm) as it is long (8 mm); when viewed from above, displays a triangular shape (Figs 3 & 8); anterior edge of the abdomen scalloped, decorated with three tubercles, with 11 submarginal sigilla (Fig. 9); abdomen posteriorly concave with four slightly pronounced, rounded tubercles (Figs 8 & 10); dorsum with small round to oval sigilla forming round depressions around the border as well as four on the median area (Figs 3 & 10); ventrum with strikingly wrinkled sinuous grooves around spinnerets. Legs tawny with indistinct, blackish-tinted bands with layers of short setae (Fig. 5); tibiae and metatarsi are flattened and slightly unequal, with metatarsi shorter than tibiae, tibiae I and II with a slight curve (Figs 1 & 9). Epigyne concave at the base with two oval, transverse concavities and upward-pointed scape (Figs 6 & 7). Male unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo; South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Plot off Malmani Road, Cradle of Humankind, Krugersdorp (-26.03465, 27.69173). **Limpopo:** Krugerpos, Orighstad (-24.904, 30.549).

LIFESTYLE

The female specimen from Gauteng was collected at night from low bushes and grass near a bee hive with a sweepnet. She was kept in a terrarium for observation. She was active at night, spinning irregular lines of strong silk between twigs and grass. During the day she rested on the ground not on supplied vegetation. Unfortunately she died after a few days.

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